

THE TERM 'WARFARE' IN A MODERN GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Within the paper, the author provides an interdisciplinary analysis of the terms "warfare", "asymmetric warfare" and "hybrid warfare". These forms of warfare have an impact on global, regional, and national security. In the final part of the paper, the author concludes: hybrid warfare is a characteristic of the 4th generation of warfare, with non-military means, such as diplomacy, economics, energy resources, information, and media are engaged to achieve goals. Terrorist organizations and criminal networks participate as the most important non-state actors. Non-state actors can have profound effects on the economic or political situation in nation-states, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region. The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a disadvantageous military position, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory.

For an effective national response to asymmetric threats, response mechanisms must be institutionalized by the national military and state institutions.

In the framework of preparing the content of the paper, the author uses the following research methods: the descriptive method, the normative method, the comparative method and the content analysis method as a special scientific method.

As a basic methodological procedure or technique for collecting data, the author uses content analysis of domestic and international references, research papers, publications, reports, conference proceedings, briefs, and analyses of various articles, journals and content analysis of websites, legal documents – regulations of the European Union, analysis of strategies, international documents, reports and Internet sources.

Keywords: warfare, asymmetric threats, hybrid warfare, state actors, non-state actors

1. INTRODUCTION

The post-Cold War period brought new low-intensity risks, such as: terrorism, civil wars, organized crime, insurgency, sabotage actions, cyber warfare, as well as other newer forms of threats, such as: warfare in urban environments, as well as the use of cruise, or ballistic missiles, to target areas that are otherwise inaccessible.

In short, post-Cold War society forced state and non-state actors to employ irregular tactics in warfare to combat the escalating arms race between opposing ideological blocs.

These conditions are directly responsible for the shift from conventional to unconventional warfare – and represent further encouragement for the use of asymmetric threats and hybrid tactics.

According to certain authors, asymmetry is an integral part of the history of society and warfare, that is, asymmetric issues have a history as long as humanity (Johnson, 2001).

In the last two decades, the buzzword "asymmetry" has been used to explain diverse and unpredictable threats that vary in intensity and common tactics and weapons (especially terrorism and crime). But when an adversary emerges that, in a planned and organized manner, simultaneously wages war symmetrically and asymmetrically, that combination necessitates a new definition: "hybrid warfare".

Scientific justification of the paper – exploring the terms "warfare", "hybrid warfare" is an important scientific content related to the struggle to tackle hybrid threats in order to achieve global stability and peace.

When preparing the paper, the author uses general methods, including descriptive, normative, comparative, and content analysis methods. The author uses the Descriptive Method – a general method that allows for a deeper insight and study of the nature of the phenomenon itself, which is the subject of the research; (this method contributes to the development of science). The subject of research is warfare, asymmetric threats, hybrid threats, etc. Dealing with these threats is an important condition for achieving global peace, security and stability.

Comparative method – the author analyses the term warfare through historical development (evolution) and comparative analysis of the terms asymmetric warfare (hybrid warfare).

Representatives from various academic disciplines are engaged in major debates over the definition of war; the types of warfare; and why wars occur.

As a basic methodological procedure or data collection technique, the author uses the analysis of the content of domestic and international references, research papers, publications, reports, conference materials, web content analysis, strategies analysis, international documents.

Through the Method of Analysis, the subject of research is broken down into its component parts, its factors, its connections and relationships in a specific space and at a specific time, thus enabling a more substantial understanding of the phenomenon being researched.

2. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERMS "WAR" AND "WARFARE"

Throughout history, there has been a marked difference in the relative military, economic, political power, and warfare strategy of warring states. It is observed that the character and nature of war are changing, especially in wars between state and non-state actors.

There are major debates in academia about the definition of war; the types of warfare; and why wars happen. Representatives from various academic disciplines have separately attempted to provide answers to these questions.

War is defined as an armed conflict between two or more governments or states.

Carl von Clausewitz, a Prussian general and military theorist active during the Napoleonic Wars, provided several definitions of warfare: once as "[the] continuation of policy by other means", while later as "...nothing but a duel on an extensive scale" and "... an act of violence intended to compel our opponent to fulfil our will" (Carl von Clausewitz, Colonel J.J. Graham, 1832).

Michael Walzer (2000), author of *Just and Unjust Wars*, defines war as "a legal state that equally permits two or more groups to engage in armed conflict" (Walzer, 2000:41).

When such conflicts become global in scope, they are known as world wars. War between different sections or factions within the same nation is called a civil war. Conflicts or wars in which major powers deliberately refrain from using all their armed power are often called limited wars (Singh, 1995). Interstate wars generally end with a treaty, and civil wars with a declaration of peace.

In the era of postmodern warfare, the character and nature of war are changing due to technological, social and cultural advances. At the same time, it is observed that warfare is dominated by the use of unconventional tactics. War and warfare have transformed from state-centric to a state where (state interest) no longer dictates combat (Creveld, 1991). Hence, there are two approaches to defining war in the postmodern era. One approach is based on technological advances and is state-centric in character. The second approach is based on the use of unconventional means and tactics and is more synonymous with non-state entities. Today, the action of a non-state actor against a state is loosely referred to as an act of asymmetric warfare. Such warfare is considered to pose a threat to become the leading instrument of strategic power (Lele, 2014).

In this context, the term asymmetry encompasses various tactics of war – fighting like guerrilla warfare, terrorism, irregular warfare, etc. these wars originate from conflicts over scarce resources, ethnic and religious issues, transnational crime (with its linkage to terrorism and insurgency), migration and illegal immigration, border disputes, famine and state collapse (Mendel, 1995-96).

"Conflict" can be described as a clash of opposing blocs, caused by ideological, territorial, economic, or other disagreements. We define the term "warfare" as "sustained, coordinated violence between political organizations" (Jack S. Levy and William R. Thompson, 2010).

This definition highlights several components of warfare.

First, war is violent. Warfare involves the use of force to kill people and destroy. This violence must be sustained to qualify as warfare, and is an exclusionary factor when classifying something as a conflict or war. Conflicts and disputes are common in international relations, but rarely do they escalate to war; such an escalation would require violence, the use of force, and then sustaining this violence for a period of time. A second component in identifying war emphasizes the "between" in our definition. Violence must be reciprocated to qualify as war; thus we treat war as the outcome of the behaviour of two or more actors.

In academic literature, warfare is classified into four distinct "generations". Each generation is characterized by a radically different strategy of warfare (Huseyin Kuru, 2018:13).

The "Classical Warfare" generation (Generation 1), and includes the Napoleonic Wars:

- The 1st generation prevails and is determined by the characteristics of the so-called Napoleonic Wars and the wars after them (the framework of the nineteenth century), where human potential and the number of armies in the conflict prevailed;

- The 2nd generation, which roughly dates back to the time around World War I (the first decade of the twentieth century), where the dominance was on the side of technology and technical innovations in armaments, i.e. firepower;

"All Along with Industry" (Generation 2), includes World War I: the Industrial Revolution and the wider availability of railways led to auxiliary and infantry units;

- The 3rd generation – "Manoeuvring wars" (Generation 3) – this is the era from World War II to the mid-1980s, where the dominant component was the ability to

manoeuvre; It is identified with the concept of national security developed by the United States in response to the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, aimed at non-governmental organizations (Hezbollah, Hamas, Al Qaeda).

The 4th generation represents the coordinated and simultaneous use of nonviolent and violent forms of civil protest, combined with special operations, with the intensive use of political, economic and social instruments, to break the enemy's combat capabilities, the morale of the organizational system. According to this theory, classical state conflicts have become a relic of the past.

This generation of wars is associated with the emergence of "Unconventional Wars" (including the aftermath of September 11 and the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq) (Renz, B., and Smith H., 2016:5).

As confirmed above, the fourth generation deviates considerably from the tactics of previous wars and encompasses asymmetric and hybrid methods unique to modern conflict.

This focuses on the ability of weaker forces to combine conventional and irregular tactics to pose a legitimate threat to the political will of the adversary. As such, fourth generation (which represents hybrid warfare) does not seek to win by defeating the enemy's military forces, but rather through hybrid tactics aimed at the enemy's political will (Mitrović, 2017).

Today, the modern geopolitical scene is a testing ground for hybrid warfare and its concept is very close to the 4th generation of warfare, - non-military means, such as diplomacy, economics, energy, information and intensive use of the media are engaged to achieve goals.

At the same time, current conflicts (hybrid wars) can also be called 5th generation of conflicts – although there is no clearly defined position of the scientific community, due to the increased form of conflict and the achieved deviation from 4th generation wars.

In the mid-20th century, British strategic theorist B.H. Liddell Hart advocated an "indirect approach" to strategy and determined that the wisest strategy avoids an enemy's strength and examines weakness (and exploits and abuses that weakness).

The complexity of the analyses of the concept of asymmetric security threats also contains deeper philosophical and socio-psychological roots.

According to Beyerchen – the very consideration of concepts such as periodicity, asymmetry, disproportionality is confusing and can cause logical repulsion, based on rootedness in cultural heritage – that is, linear concepts are far simpler and more acceptable than considerations of "unstable" concepts such as asymmetry and nonlinearity (Beyerchen, 1992).

Military historian John Keegan proposed this in his political-rational theory of war, saying that "[warfare] is assumed to be an orderly affair involving states, with declared beginnings and ends, easily identifiable combatants, and a high level of obedience on the part of subordinates" (Keegan, 1993). According to Keegan, this theory deals poorly with non-state and unconventional tactics.

Unlike nation-states (in the upper echelons of military spending), weaker parties to a conflict must bypass direct attacks in favour of unexpected tactics, due to their own shortcomings as well as the superiority of their adversary. These asymmetric approaches employ innovative, non-traditional tactics and weapons or technologies that are irregular in nature (Brzica, 2018:34).

3. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERM ASYMMETRIC WARFARE

Asymmetry means the absence of a common basis for comparison in terms of some quality or, in operational terms, capability. All conflicts are asymmetrical to some extent, and the skilled fighter has always exploited this characteristic.

In war, there are always differences between the opponents. Sometimes, those differences are insignificant, fleeting – with no impact on the outcome.

There are situations in which the differences between opponents are important, putting one at an advantage and the other at a disadvantage. This is a very simple observation, but it raises one of the burning questions – and that is STRATEGIC ASYMMETRY:

Strategic asymmetry is the use of some difference to gain an advantage over the opponent. This is an idea as old as warfare itself (which appears in numerous forms, guises) (See: https://repository.ukim.mk/bitstream/20.500.12188/2308/1/acvetanovska2019_1.pdf).

Among strategic theorists, Sun Tzu Wu establishes "The basic concept of asymmetric warfare is a model through which a technologically and numerically weaker opponent enables the infliction of losses on the opposing side, presenting results in order to promote their views and goals, with the aim of motivating new like-minded people". According to this theorist, conducting indirect forms of warfare is one of the most effective ways to combat the enemy (Sun Tzu, 2000:9).

Asymmetric warfare can be defined as: "a form of warfare in which a non-state actor uses unconventional means and tactics against a state's vulnerabilities to achieve disproportionate effect, undermining the state's will to achieve its strategic goals".

Steven Metz, an American national security expert at the US Army War College, defines "asymmetry" as "acting, organizing, and thinking differently from adversaries to maximize relative strengths, exploit an adversary's weaknesses, or gain greater freedom of action" (Metz, S., Johnson, 2001).

Asymmetric warfare can be defined as: "a form of warfare in which a non-state actor uses unconventional means and tactics against a state's vulnerabilities to achieve disproportionate effect, undermining the state's will to achieve its strategic goals".

The successful asymmetric tactics used by non-state actors over the past few decades demonstrate that asymmetric warfare is a contest of wills. Psychological defeat is often much more serious and longer-lasting than battlefield defeat. The easiest way to achieve this is to attack the enemy where he feels most comfortable and secure (Goulding, 2000-01).

The goal is to achieve an advantage or defeat the enemy without directly engaging one's military operatives and expending one's own resources, which would inevitably cause direct conflict.

One of the main characteristics of asymmetric threats – avoiding the classical method of warfare – is seen in the fact that the organizers – the subjects of asymmetric action (organization, groups, states) avoid, through their actions, entering into a direct, open armed conflict with the state that is the target of the action. It acts indirectly – through the application of new tactics and the development of operational capabilities, as well as the use of technical and unconventional means.

These actions are coordinated, synchronized, and directed at the vulnerabilities, or weaknesses, of the chosen target. They can be directed at any domain of society – political, economic, military, civilian, or informational. Vulnerability is a qualitative characteristic of a state, which reflects the likelihood that the state will be attacked or harmed.

Based on certain analyses, it is possible to conditionally determine the determinants of asymmetric warfare: (Mitrović, 2017).

- an asymmetric threat to security is represented by phenomena that are new, unusual, surprising and unexpected threats;
- asymmetric threats are conditioned by the position and attitudes of certain nation states according to global foreign and security policy;
- the environment for the development of asymmetric threats is conditioned by the circumstances faced by institutions in the state – circumstances that have an impact on international security relations.
- the classical, conventional approach to organizing the defence and security system of a state (in the current dynamic movement) is relatively outdated and shows organizational weaknesses and shortcomings in the security system and the defence system; hence latent institutional weaknesses emerge in the current, classical way of responding to security threats and is predominantly focused on preventing and eliminating consequences, and less on prevention and building a protection system. According to certain authors, asymmetry aims to disrupt security forces – using their weaknesses – with an asymmetric approach based on psychological effects.
- the existence and application of new tactics and development of operational capabilities as well as technical and unconventional means of action by the adversary.

One of the main characteristics of asymmetric threats is to avoid the classical method of warfare, which is perceived through the fact that the organizers, the subjects of asymmetric action (the organization, the states) avoid, through their actions, entering into a direct, open armed conflict with the state that is the target of the action. There are situations when the bearers of asymmetric action are organized, supported or directed by other sponsoring states, acting against the victim state (according to perceived weaknesses in society, socio-economic and political life, as well as individual critical weak points of a particular state's infrastructure or defence and security system) (Mitrović, 2017).

In this way, the bearer of the asymmetric actions is placed in a position to implement the hybrid form of warfare that the sponsor implements, and they become an intermediary in the pursuit of other people's interests.

Practically, the asymmetric approach is based on exploiting an opponent's weakness, using innovative, non-traditional tactics, weapons and technology, and can be applied at all levels and types of warfare - strategic, operational and tactical, as well as across the entire spectrum of military operations (Staff, 1992:2). Asymmetric threats involve a variety of tactics, including disinformation campaigns, terrorism, and cyberattacks.

Asymmetric threats include a variety of tactics, including disinformation campaigns, terrorism, and cyberattacks. Importantly, these tactics exist under the threshold for conventional conflict while still de-stabilizing governments, alliances, or organizations (Beaulieu, and Salvo, 2018:1).

According to the Ministry of Defence in Serbia, certain characteristics are inherently asymmetric: 1. 2. 3. 4. 5. considered unusual from a conventional point of view (i.e. torture); irregular in the sense that they violate treaties or laws of armed conflict; depart from war as previously understood, (as in flying planes into buildings); leveraged or specialized against assets; difficult to respond to proportionally, creating a situation where

military intervention in response seems inhumane or cruel; 6. having unforeseen circumstances, typical of an event or attack not previously used. (Ćurčić, 2018).

Stephen Blank, a senior fellow at the Foreign Policy Research Institute, offers another interpretation of asymmetry, called "Blank's Theory" (Stephen Blank, 2020).

Blank's theory classifies asymmetric threats into five dimensions: 1. "they are threats of an unconventional nature; 2. 3. 4. 5. they are designed to mislead the adversary; they can be used by both state and non-state actors; they do not imply confrontation; and; they reflect the adversary's strategy". In both scenarios, these tactics are completely flexible, and create military action that is unpredictable, irregular, and difficult to combat.

4. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERM HYBRID WARFARE

Hybrid warfare exists alongside asymmetric threats, mixing conventional and irregular tactics. In this sense, hybrid warfare "... combines military and non-military means, as well as covert and overt means, including disinformation, cyber-attacks, economic pressure [and] the deployment of irregular armed groups and the use of regular forces (Beaulieu and Salvo, 2018).

Franck Hoffman, a Distinguished Research Fellow with the Institute for National Strategic Studies, builds on this definition: he argues that hybrid warfare incorporates different modes of warfare (both conventional and asymmetric capabilities), thereby utilizing synergistic efforts that are simultaneous, fused, and subordinate to one command unit (Hoffman, 2007:8).

According to some military experts, this unconventional theatre of conflict can further be described as the "Gray Zone" of warfare, characterized by "...intense political, economic, informational and military competition more fervent than steady-state diplomacy, yet short of conventional war", and employing "small-footprint, low-visibility operations often of a covert or clandestine nature".

According to some military experts, hybrid warfare represents a "Gray Zone" of warfare, and is characterized by "...intense political, economic, informational, and military competition more fierce than steady-state diplomacy, yet less so than conventional warfare" and which utilizes "small-scale, low-visibility operations, often of a covert nature" (Joseph L. Votel, Charles T. Cleveland, Charles T. Connett, and Will Irwin, 2016:102).

The London-based International Institute for Strategic Studies in 2015 gave the following definition of "hybrid warfare": "The use of military and non-military instruments in an integrated campaign to achieve surprise, seize initiative, and gain psychological advantage used in diplomatic actions; large-scale and rapid information, electronic, and cyber operations; covert and covert military and intelligence activities; combined with economic pressure". The definition accurately reflects the key differences between hybrid wars and traditional conflicts.

The terrorist attacks of September 11 and the subsequent geopolitical consequences modelled a growing convergence of non-state and state forces. This created a void in contemporary military terminology and strategy, filled today by the widely used term "asymmetric and hybrid threats" (Ćurčić, 2018:23).

According to political experts, it is clear that hybrid warfare uses a combination of tactics – conventional tactics and asymmetric tactics are used, as well as strategic and simultaneously coordinated efforts that are different from those of previous wars.

Forms through which hybrid warfare manifests are (information operations, separatist and secessionist movements, "colour revolutions", institutionalized religious,

national and political extremism, counterterrorism, unconventional warfare, foreign internal defence (support of other countries in external aggression), stabilization operations, security transitions, reconstruction, strategic communications, psychological operations, information operations, civil-military operations, intelligence and counterintelligence operations, economic and energy sanctions and other general sanctions (in sports, culture, science).

5. DETERMINING THE TERMS STATE ACTORS AND NON-STATE ACTORS

Today, changes in global centres of power affect a number of regional and local events and processes. These changes also affect the challenges and threats to global and national security.

Today, in the realization of their interests, state and non-state entities are not guided by classic forms of conflict, are not guided by classical warfare. At the same time, the effects of the engagement of funds and forces lead to evident changes, in the field of real geopolitics on the ground, as well as in the fields of influence and effects of the effects of strategic advantage and positioning of powerful global and regional forces. Hence, the emergence of conflicts by applying unconventional means.

The strengthening of the power of non-state actors further complicates the security situation in the world. Non-state actors are (criminal groups, foreign-funded extremists, foreign fighters, returnees, terrorists, etc.). State actors are capable (and willing) to organize asymmetric efforts – their position regarding asymmetric conflict generally differs from that of non-state actors and is therefore considered separately.

The state contains traditional military and political authority that relies on its own economic and diplomatic power. In comparison, non-state actors use a non-hierarchical structure of motivated "cells" with shared motivations and political goals (Brzica, 2018:41).

State and non-state actors are inherently different, especially in terms of sovereignty: according to a report published by the National Intelligence Council, non-state actors are non-sovereign entities and therefore lack legitimacy on the global stage (See the contents on Non-State Actors: Impact on International Relations and Implications for the United States”, National Intelligence Council, National Intelligence Officer for Economics and Global Issues (August 23, 2007:2).

However, understanding both actors is vital to any discussion of asymmetric and hybrid warfare.

State actors

According to Timofey Bordachev, a professor at the Higher School of Economics, a state is a politically organized body of people in a defined territory with public authority and the legitimate use of force and violence. This monopoly on violence distinguishes sovereign states from other actors that lack similar territory or authority. State actors represent the traditional consolidation of authority and the central elements of the international system. Furthermore, a state must have public authority, governance tools, and a territory and population to govern (Timofei Bordachev and Dmitrii Suslov, 2018).

Beyond legality, some states conduct conflict beyond their borders, operating armies large enough to warrant conventional conflict or relying on hybrid and asymmetric means to circumvent international law with potential consequences.

In both states with conventional warfare capabilities and those waging proxy wars abroad, asymmetric threats have proven effective in causing massive disruptions to

national governments and supranational organizations. Every nation-state needs to create a defence strategy to fully address a specific asymmetric threat.

Non-state actors

Non-state actors are defined as "non-sovereign entities that exercise political, economic, or social" control at the national or international level (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2). These actors operate outside the boundaries of the conventional state, pursuing their political agendas through means that are more difficult to constrain or regulate. Building consensus on non-state actors has proven difficult for both scholars and national governments. However, a flexible list includes the following, according to the United States National Intelligence Council:

2. multinational corporations and organizations; non-governmental organizations (NGOs); 3. 4. 5. superpowers; terrorist organizations; criminal networks (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2).

Terrorist organizations and criminal networks participate as the most important non-state actors. When examining conflict, two main groups of non-state actors can be identified according to their operational tendencies. Non-violent non-state actors, including multinational corporations, can have profound effects on the economic or political state of a nation, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2).

Violent non-state actors generally cause national and international consequences of extreme magnitude and are characterized by their ability to rely on violence and force through asymmetric channels. Militias, warlords, insurgents, terrorist and criminal gangs, and transnational criminal groups all exemplify the range of violent non-state actors (Thomas Risse, Tanja A. Börzel, and Anke Draude, ed. 2018).

The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a military disadvantage, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory. This is evident when examining specific examples of non-state actors and their methods, such as terrorist organizations operating in the Middle East, Africa, or Southeast Asia.

RUSSIA'S ATTACK ON UKRAINE – HYBRID WARFARE

By analysing the activities of the Russian Federation, Western military experts conclude that hybrid warfare is characterized by the following principles: (Janev, 2021)

- analysing the opponent - through the use of scientific methods (the goal is to identify and exploit the opponent's vulnerabilities, especially at a strategic level);
- developing a coherent strategy – by connecting all military instruments (conventional, irregular, nuclear) and civilian instruments of the state structure.
- applying strategies ambiguously. Be unpredictable in your actions and flexibly adapt your strategies to meet unforeseen opportunities and risks;
- refraining from publicly declaring and ending war. Conventional war should last as short as possible, while the hybrid threat can last indefinitely;
- using time as a strategic advantage - through the use of covert strategies, strategic deception, and strategic surprise;
- using armed forces regardless of strategic defeat – military assets are used, military actions are taken to threaten and pressure civilian actors on the opposing side, as well as to deter the opponent from possible military actions;

- striving to achieve dominance in the information space in relation to the enemy - at all levels of warfare (strategic, operational and tactical), through the application of complex information operations.

After Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the threat of so-called "hybrid warfare" has increased significantly. "Hybrid warfare" is the expansion of a purely military combat operation using espionage, sabotage, cyberattacks, election influence, propaganda or disinformation campaigns to weaken and destabilize the enemy from within. Experts warn that Russia has been continuously expanding its arsenal of hybrid warfare capabilities in recent years (See: <https://www.dw.com/mk/kako-funkcionira-ruskata-hibridna-vojna/a-70908400>).

In 2022, Germany was the target of a series of sabotage attacks: an arson attack at the Diehl factory that produces Iris-T air defence systems; an explosive device that caused a fire at the DHL hub in Leipzig; the destruction of parked military trucks in Erfurt; and sabotage of German warships, including damaged cables and contaminated water systems (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e-napadnata/>).

Poland was targeted with fires in shopping malls, warehouses, including an IKEA facility – operations that the investigation linked to Russian intelligence services. In the United Kingdom, a DHL warehouse in Birmingham was hit by an incendiary attack carried out by operatives of the Russian Main Intelligence Directorate (GRU – Главное разведывательное управление). France and Estonia have reported similar cases, accompanied by disinformation campaigns to sow fear and distrust.

Espionage – Since the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, European countries have expelled about 500 Russian diplomats. The British secret service MI5 classifies at least 400 of them as spies. There are speculations that many Russian embassies and consulates have state-of-the-art communications and spying technology. The claim cannot be confirmed with certainty because the facilities are considered Russian sovereign territory and enjoy diplomatic status and protection. The Dutch secret service has warned that Russia is providing false documents for spies and infiltrating Western institutions as businessmen.

Sabotage – A Chinese cargo ship commanded by a Russian captain damaged two submarine cables with the anchor it was dragging along the seabed. (November 2024). In October 2024, a fire was set at a warehouse in London storing aid for Ukraine. In July 2024, a package intended for air transport was set on fire at the DHL logistics centre in Leipzig. In these and numerous other cases, there are suspicions of Russian sabotage (however, nothing has been proven so far).

European intelligence services are warning that the number of acts of sabotage and arson in the EU and the UK has increased dramatically in the past 2024 year.

Cyber Attacks – The German Federal Office for Information Security warns that the spectrum of threats in cyberspace has expanded. “Before the Russian attack on Ukraine, groups linked to Russia were particularly active in Germany with cyber espionage and financially motivated attacks.

For example, there has been a sharp increase in the number of “DDoS attacks by pro-Russian hacktivists”, i.e. the flooding of institutional websites or servers to the point where they can no longer be managed due to overload. Hacker attacks aimed at penetrating the protected networks of companies or institutions are also on the rise.

Disinformation and Propaganda – Another area of hybrid warfare activity is the attempt to influence public opinion in the targeted country. False information, as well as pro-Russian or anti-Ukrainian narratives, are spread through so-called troll factories on social media or through Russian media abroad. In early 2024, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs uncovered a campaign in which 50,000 fake user accounts were spreading false allegations and pro-Russian opinions on social media, linked to fake websites. Some of them resembled well-known news outlets (except that they were spreading pro-Russian fake news).

Interference in elections and political processes - The primary goal of these disinformation campaigns is to undermine support for Ukraine among the population. Another goal is to undermine political stability in the (democratic) targeted country by strengthening extremist parties and their candidates - for example, through financial support. In April 2024, the Czech secret service uncovered the propaganda website "Voice of Europe", which was allegedly funded by Moscow and used to bribe various European lawmakers.

Western intelligence agencies accuse Russia of directly or indirectly interfering in dozens of elections in Europe and North and South America. For example, the Russian foreign broadcaster RT produced videos during the US presidential election campaign on controversial topics such as aid to Ukraine, migration or the economy. One can also cite Russian attacks with leaks of confidential data from politicians or parties, sometimes even mixed with forged documents, which are published shortly before elections. This happened in the 2016 US elections, or in the 2017 French presidential campaign.

For its hybrid war against Europe, Russia has created a network of agents, linking state agencies and the criminal underworld. Russian-speaking men with criminal records are also being recruited to carry out sabotage in Europe - This is the conclusion of experts from the NGO GLOBSEQ and the International Counter-Terrorism Centre (ICCT) in a joint study titled "Russian Criminal-Terrorist Network: Crime as a Tool for Hybrid Warfare in Europe". (See: <https://www.dw.com/mk/ruskata-mreza-za-hibridna-vojna-vo-evropa-kako-kreml-go-koristi-podzemjeto-za-sabotazi/a-74688707>).

The study places Moscow's tactics in the context of the war in Ukraine. It shows that "hybrid operations are not a sideshow, but a central pillar of Russian strategy". The researchers compare such tactics to the methods of the Islamic State (IS), a terrorist organization that once recruited criminals in Europe. "But this time it is not a terrorist organization, but a state actor that is driving recruitment and operations", the study emphasizes.

According to the study, from January 2022 to July 2025, there were 110 sabotage attempts and attacks with links to Russia in Europe, mostly in Poland and France. 89 of them were successful, and 21 were thwarted. The study authors emphasize that the number of thwarted sabotage attempts is likely significantly higher because intelligence agencies do not always disclose such information to the public. Furthermore, experts have identified

131 individuals who were involved in the incidents. At least 35 of them are former convicts and were recruited in prison or through criminal organizations.

According to the study, the Kremlin primarily recruits men in their 30s for sabotage operations in Europe – most often from post-Soviet countries, Russian-speaking, and in difficult living circumstances. Recruitment often takes place online, usually via Telegram, or through relatives and friends. The main incentive for saboteurs is money, with sums ranging from a few euros for distributing pro-Russian leaflets to significant sums for attempted attacks on critical infrastructure, the study states. To finance these activities, Moscow is also using illegal means to circumvent Western sanctions. "Russia's military campaign - bombings, arson, assassination attempts - should be seen as both a punishment for Europe's support for Ukraine, and a preparation for a potentially larger conflict".

GLOBSEC Recommendations for Defence Against Hybrid Threats - As a further step, the definition of “hybrid threats” should be expanded because the national doctrines and strategies of many countries do not adequately take into account the role of “non-state actors such as criminal organizations, ideologically motivated intermediaries, or individuals acting for personal gain”. It is precisely these “legal loopholes” that allow Russia to deny its guilt or involvement in attacks and acts of sabotage. It further states that close cooperation between public and private actors is crucial in combating this threat. "They must be partners, as private companies in Europe have more sophisticated mechanisms for detecting Russian criminal activities. It is necessary to create a platform for coordinating cooperation in order to prevent Russian hybrid attacks on European countries".

Russia’s war does not end at Ukraine’s borders. Hybrid warfare – a combination of conventional force and covert, unconventional tactics – has become a permanent feature of the Kremlin’s strategy to weaken European cohesion, disrupt critical infrastructure, undermine trust in democratic institutions, and influence political processes, all without crossing the line into open warfare (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e-napadnata/>).

The European Union continuously condemns Russia's hybrid campaigns against the EU, its Member States and partners, which encompass a deliberate and systematic pattern of malicious behaviour, including cyber and physical attacks, acts of sabotage, damage to critical infrastructure, manipulation, the spread of disinformation and other covert or violent activities, which have further escalated since the beginning of the Russian aggression against Ukraine (See: <https://www.brif.mk/sankciite-na-eu-poradi-ruskite-hibridni-zakani-prodolzheni-za-ushte-edna-godina/>).

Hybrid warfare is designed to disrupt and deplete societies politically, economically and psychologically. It aims to disintegrate alliances, undermine trust in democratic institutions and create divisions along ethnic, cultural or ideological lines. Recognizing and exposing strategies and tactics, their sources and objectives is essential to protecting democracy, stability and security of states (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e-napadnata/>).

As democratic institutions across Europe and the world face the growing threat of disinformation and the consequences of hybrid warfare, the fabric of European democracy is under threat. In addition to conventional warfare and brutal war crimes and destruction

of civilian targets in Ukraine, Russia's ongoing campaign to destabilize the West consists of infiltrating the economy, politics, and society.

CONCLUSION

The extreme differences in the military capabilities of actors have encouraged the use of asymmetric and hybrid threats. In other words, there is an inequality between actors with the capacity to accumulate large armies and those without the capacity to accumulate large armies. This has created an environment where less powerful actors must resort to employing hybrid tactics to reduce the inequality. Non-state actors can have profound effects on the economic or political situation in nation-states, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region. The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a disadvantageous military position, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory.

Modern national states still do not have functional hybrid threat response systems. These states need to face the challenge of hybrid, asymmetric threats of the 21st century in order to defend themselves against unconventional threats and maintain internal cohesion. These countries need to take greater responsibility for building resilience within their own societies to protect their security and sovereignty. It is necessary to adopt a national strategy for dealing with hybrid threats and building resistance.

The NATO Alliance also applies a strategy to counter hybrid warfare (See: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_156338.htm?fbclid=IwAR2dS8IfODGxxr8B3RfenvBHdCsuetzj7aL9i4lFt-8GdUODX3GD-Mk).

The NATO Alliance is continuously collecting, sharing and evaluating information in order to detect and prescribe a certain current hybrid activity. The NATO Headquarters Joint Intelligence and Security Department improves the understanding and analysis of the Alliance for Hybrid Threats.

NATO also serves as a centre for expertise, providing support to allies in areas such as civilian readiness and response to chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) incidents; protection of critical infrastructure; strategic communications; protection of civilians; cyber defence; Energy security and the fight against terrorism. Training, exercises and education also play an important role in preparing for opposition to hybrid threats. This involves conducting decision-making processes and joint military and non-military responses in collaboration with other actors.

For an effective national response to asymmetrical threats, the response mechanisms must be institutionalized.

Integrated and institutionalized defence effort should include two basic efforts: threat protection and management. The answers must be institutionalized by the national army and state institutions. It is necessary to create a policy and strategy for dealing with hybrid threats and building resistance.

Through the Security Union Strategy – 2024, The European Union establishes activities aimed at achieving the strategic goal – strengthening the security of citizens in the European Union;

The European Union has continued to develop tools for effectively dealing with hybrid threats. These tools include: (According to Council document 7371/22).

- A European Union's hybrid box that is a framework in order to provide a coordinated and well-informed response to hybrid threats and campaigns;

- Hybrid teams for rapid response to the European Union have been formed in order to provide support to member states, countries and missions and operations of joint security and defence policy (CSDP);
 - EU protocol has been revised to counter hybrid threats ("The EU Protocol on Countering Hybrid Threats ("EU Play") that describes the processes and structures of the Union that deal with hybrid threats and campaigns
 - Instructions for the implementation of the EU Common Diplomatic Response Framework for malicious cyber activities have been revised, ("Cyber Diplomacy Tools") that enables the development of sustainable, adjustable, coherent and coordinated strategies against the constant actors of the cyber threat.
 - The existing tools of the Union for Prevention, Detection and Response to Manipulation and Mixing with Foreign Information (Jimmy) are also strengthened.
- Member States are taking action to continue and improve their cooperation in this area by ensuring effective implementation of the above tools. In this regard, regular exercises were carried out and hybrid teams were formed to give a quick response.

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